

Extended Standardmodel

$$ESM = SU(5)_s \times SU(3)_c \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_{y1} \times U(1)_{y2}$$

s...sense charges

c...color charges

L...isospin

y...hypercharge

by Mag.rer.nat.KronbergerReinhard

Email : support@kro4pro.com

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Introduction :

This symmetries arises by the symmetries of the coxeter element of the affine group E9 which is the affine one point extension of the well known exceptional group E8.

Why do we consider the E9 group (more specifically the Coxeter element of this group)?

1) E9 is an affine group and thus has something to do with extension.

2) The extension is flat as the universe.

3) The action of the Coxeter elements of the group produces symmetries involving our current standard model.

The fundamentals here :

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Coxeter_group

<https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wurzelsystem>

<http://home.mathematik.uni-freiburg.de/soergel/Skripten/XXSPIEG.pdf>

Dynkin Diagram E9 (affine one point extension of group E8) :

$\tilde{E}_9$

Derivative of the symmetries of ESM from the invariants of the Coxeter elements E9.

A Coxeter element is a product of the generating reflections of E9.

For example : Coxeter element = e1.e2.e3.e4.e5.e6.e7.e8.e9

The Coxeter polynomial is the characteristic polynomial of Coxeter elements and has the form :

$$E_9(x) = \frac{x^5 - 1}{x - 1} \cdot \frac{x^3 - 1}{x - 1} \cdot \frac{x^2 - 1}{x - 1} \cdot (x - 1)^2$$

$$E_9CS = SU(5) \times SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)^2$$

$E_9(x)$... characteristic polynomial of the coxeter element of E9

$E_9(x)$ is a polynomial with terms of cyclotomic factors $Z_n = \frac{x^n - 1}{x - 1}$
for $n > 1$ and $(x - 1)$ for $n = 1$.

The cyclotomic factors are the characteristic polynomial of the A_{n-1} which is the Dynkin diagram for the $SU(n)$ Liegroup.

See more here : https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Special_unitary_group.

So finally the symmetry space by the actions of the Coxeter elements is

$$SU(5) \times SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1) \times U(1)$$

Hint :

Our symmetry is a special case of the models given by

$$SU(n_1) \times SU(n_2) \times \dots \times SU(n_k) \times U(1)^{k-1}$$

If we set $n_1 = 5, n_2 = 3, n_3 = 2$ and $k = 3$ then we get our ESM.

What bring us the additional symmetries?

- (1) These have the potential to describe new particles.
- (2) These have the potential to describe the space and time.
- (3) These have the potential to describe gravity.

< 1 > The Idea

Light and gravitation just like photon and graviton have something in common.

Both are massless and propagate with the speed of light.

We know that light by the

Symmetry breaking 1 : $SU(2) \times U(1) \rightarrow U(1)e$ is described as a mixture.

So light is a part of the electro - weak interactions.

we consider analog gravity as a result of a further symmetry breaking

Symmetry breaking 2 : $SU(5) \times U(1) \times U(1) \rightarrow U(1)g$

Our extended standard model allows us this.

We will now like to assign our relevant $SU(n)$'s to division algebras (real numbers, complex numbers, ...).

$$SU(1) \longleftrightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

$$SU(2) \longleftrightarrow \mathbb{C}$$

$$SU(3) \longleftrightarrow \mathbb{H}$$

$$SU(5) \longleftrightarrow \mathbb{O}$$

This 4 division algebras can be generated by the doubling process

(see more at <https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Verdopplungsverfahren>).

Considering the rank of the $SU(2) = 1, SU(3) = 2, SU(5) = 4$ then this is double as well.

There appears to be a connection between the division algebras and the $SU(n)$ ($n = 2, 3, 5$).

The connections are the rank (maximal torus) of the $SU(n)$ and the orthogonal complex subspaces of the division algebra.

For example the quaternions have two orthogonal complex subspaces

$a + b.i1$ and $c.i2 + d.i3$ (a, b, c, d real).

The $SU(3)$ has also 2 neutral elements (toris).

With this assignment we can create backgroundfields to the $SU(3)$ and $SU(5)$ like it is the higgsfield for $SU(2)$.

$SU(1) \leftrightarrow \mathbb{R}^1$ real singlet
 $SU(2) \leftrightarrow \mathbb{C}^2$ complex dublet higgsfield
 $SU(3) \leftrightarrow \mathbb{H}^3$ quaternionic triplet
 $SU(5) \leftrightarrow \mathbb{O}^5$ octonionic quintet Octoquintenfield

Therefore, we rely analogously on the Higgsfield ($2 \times$ complex = doublet).

$$\phi = \begin{bmatrix} \phi^+ \\ \phi^0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_1^+ + i.\phi_2^+ \\ \phi_1^0 + i.\phi_2^0 \end{bmatrix}$$

< 2 > the Octoquintenfield ($5 \times$ Octonions = Quintet).

$$\phi = \begin{bmatrix} \phi^G \\ \phi^R \\ \phi^F \\ \phi^S \\ \phi^O \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_0^G + i_1.\phi_1^G + i_2.\phi_2^G + i_3.\phi_3^G + i_4.\phi_4^G + i_5.\phi_5^G + i_6.\phi_6^G + i_7.\phi_7^G \\ \phi_0^R + i_1.\phi_1^R + i_2.\phi_2^R + i_3.\phi_3^R + i_4.\phi_4^R + i_5.\phi_5^R + i_6.\phi_6^R + i_7.\phi_7^R \\ \phi_0^F + i_1.\phi_1^F + i_2.\phi_2^F + i_3.\phi_3^F + i_4.\phi_4^F + i_5.\phi_5^F + i_6.\phi_6^F + i_7.\phi_7^F \\ \phi_0^S + i_1.\phi_1^S + i_2.\phi_2^S + i_3.\phi_3^S + i_4.\phi_4^S + i_5.\phi_5^S + i_6.\phi_6^S + i_7.\phi_7^S \\ \phi_0^O + i_1.\phi_1^O + i_2.\phi_2^O + i_3.\phi_3^O + i_4.\phi_4^O + i_5.\phi_5^O + i_6.\phi_6^O + i_7.\phi_7^O \end{bmatrix}$$

This provides 40 degrees of freedom.

24 of which will be "spent" for our $SU(5)$ tensor bosons for the 5th longitudinal spin degree of freedom (24 Goldstone bosons swallowed over gauge transformation) thus remain 16 left.

The S, F, R, G and H charges are the 5 charges of the $SU(5)$ analogous to the 3 color charges of $SU(3)$ and the 2 charges (+, -) of $SU(2)$.

The letters stand for S = See, F = feeling, R = smelling G = Taste and H = Hear

Calling therefor the charges of the $SU(5)$ sense charges.

Note : These charges have (such as the color charges of quarks with color) nothing to do with the senses, but to give a name to the child for reference only.

We now want to look at the 16 ($40 - 24 = 16$) remaining degrees of freedom.

Make the following division for the 40 field components of the Octoquinten field as a physical approach :

Φ_H									$\mathbb{O}$
Φ_G	1	i1	i2	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7	$\mathbb{O}$
Φ_R	1	i1	i2	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7	$\mathbb{O}$
Φ_F	1	i1	i2	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7	$\mathbb{O}$
Φ_S	1	i1	i2	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7	$\mathbb{O}$
Φ_O	1	i1	i2	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7	$\mathbb{O}$ Charge 0

$\mathbb{O}^6$ or $\mathbb{O}^5$

Energy-Time
 Momentum-Space
 Shearstress/Energyflux
 for the 4 neutral Bosons
 for the 20 charged Bosons

Analogous to the Higgspotential we declare a Potential on the Octoquintenfield

< 3 > Potential over the Octoquintenfield

$$V(\phi) = \frac{\mu^2}{2} |\phi|^2 + \frac{\lambda^2}{4} |\phi|^4 + \frac{\gamma^2}{8} |\phi|^8 \quad \text{with } \phi \in \mathbb{O}^5$$

$$|\phi|^2 = \phi^\dagger \cdot \phi$$

$\gamma, \mu \in i\mathbb{R}$ (imaginaer) and $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$

$$\frac{\mu^2}{2} \dots \text{momentumdensity}^2 \quad (\rho \cdot v)^2 = \left(\frac{kg}{m^3} \cdot \frac{m}{s}\right)^2$$

$$\frac{\lambda^2}{4} \dots \text{massdensity}^2 \quad (\rho)^2 = \left(\frac{kg}{m^3}\right)^2$$

$$\frac{\gamma^2}{8} \dots \text{spindensity}^2 \quad \left(\frac{\rho}{v^2}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\frac{kg}{m^3}}{\frac{m^2}{s^2}}\right)^2$$

The coefficients of the potential comes from selfinteractions.
Therefore we make the assumption that we have the following relation :

$$C := \frac{-\lambda^2}{\gamma^2} = \left(4 \cdot \frac{\mu^2}{\lambda^2}\right)^2 \quad \gamma^2, \mu^2 < 0 \quad \lambda^2 > 0$$

Then it follows by exact calculation that

$$C = c^4 \cdot \varphi^2$$

c ...speed of light

φ ...golden ratio = 1,6180...

The first angle which comes from the minimum of the Oktoquintenpotential is appr. equal to the WEINBERG - ANGLE $\approx 28,89^\circ$
see < 8 >

Comparing the Oktoquintenpotential OQP with the standard relativistic energy (density) equation :

$$E^2 = p^2 \cdot c^2 + m^2 \cdot c^4 \quad p = \text{momentum}; m = \text{mass}$$

Our OQP has a third term and expand the equation to

$$E^2 = p^2 \cdot c^2 + m^2 \cdot c^4 + s^2 \cdot c^8$$

we call the third term the spin - term.

< 3.1 > Einstein - Form

We want that the second part of the Oktoqintenpotential is our quadratic vacuumenergydensity.

$$\frac{\lambda^2}{4} |c|^4 = \left(\frac{\Lambda \cdot c^4}{8\pi G}\right)^2 = (\varrho_{\text{vacuum}} \cdot c^2)^2$$

Λ ...cosmological constant

ϱ_{vacuum} ...vacuum massdensity

then with the relation $c^4 \cdot \varphi^2 = \frac{-\lambda^2}{\gamma^2} = \left(4 \cdot \frac{\mu^2}{\lambda^2}\right)^2$ we get the potential as

EINSTEIN – FORM

$$V(\phi) = \left(\frac{\Lambda \cdot c^4}{8\pi G}\right)^2 \cdot \left(-\frac{\varphi}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{|\phi|}{c}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{|\phi|}{c}\right)^4 - \frac{1}{2 \cdot \varphi^2} \cdot \left(\frac{|\phi|}{c}\right)^8\right)$$

We have 3 "spheres" where the potential vanishes.

The first in the center which is a point. We name it S_0 .

Then one with $|\phi| = c = 1$ which we name S_c and one with

$|\phi| = \sqrt{\varphi} \cdot c = \sqrt{\varphi}$ which we name $S_{\sqrt{\varphi}}$.

Compact $(S_0, S_c, S_{\sqrt{\varphi}})$ for the zero subspace.

Now we want to take a look on a complex subspace of our definitionrange $\mathbb{O}^5$.

For example $\mathbb{C} = \{\phi_0^0 + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^0\}$

We have 3 "cycles" $S_0, S_c, S_{\sqrt{\varphi}}$ for the 3 different curvatures elliptic, flat, hyperbolic on any point ϕ with $|\phi| = c = 1$.

The cycles build the focuspoints of the different curvatures.

The cycle S_0 which is the origin 0 is the focuspoint (centerpoint) for the elliptic curvature on c .

The cycle S_c is the set of focuspoints for the flat curvature.

The cycle $S_{\sqrt{\varphi}}$ is the set of focuspoints for the hyperbolic curvature.

This can be extended to quaternionic subspaces of our definitionrange $\mathbb{O}^5$.

For example $\mathbb{H} = \{\phi_0^0 + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^0 + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^0 + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^0\}$

Then instead of cycles S^1 we have S^3 three spheres where the potential vanishes.

< 3.2 > Getting a new particle by the Octoqintenfield of $m \approx 28$ GeV mass.

We have densities like massdensity in our Oktoquintenpotential.

How can we compare it with the Higgspotential with mass?

For this we take a look on the relation where $mass \sim \frac{1}{r}$:

$$m_r = \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\hbar}{c} \quad r \dots \text{radius, } \hbar \dots \text{Planckconstant, } c \dots \text{speed of light}$$

Then it follows that $m_r \cdot r = m_p \cdot l_p = \frac{\hbar}{c} = \text{constant}$.

$m_p \dots$ Planckmass, $l_p \dots$ Plancklength

With $\rho_m = \frac{m}{V_m}$ and from above $m^3 \cdot r^3 = m_p^3 \cdot l_p^3$ we get the relation

$$m^3 \cdot V_m = m_p^3 \cdot V_p \Rightarrow \frac{m^3}{V_p} = \frac{m_p^3}{V_m} \Rightarrow m^4 \cdot \rho_p = m_p^4 \cdot \rho_m \Rightarrow$$

$$m = m_p \cdot \left(\frac{\rho_m}{\rho_p}\right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \quad \rho_p \dots \text{Planckdensity}$$

By this way we get from a massdensity ρ_m an assigned mass m .

Can we find a 1 : 1 connection between the Higgsfield and the Oktoquintenfield?

With the quantisationformular above we can calculate a mass m_Λ for the vacuummassdensity ρ_{vac} . We will write for $\rho_{vac} = \rho_\Lambda$

We know ρ_p (Planckmassdensity), m_p (Planckmass) and ρ_Λ (Vacuummassdensity).

Then we get by the formulare above for m_Λ :

$$m_\Lambda \approx 4,032113 \times 10^{-39} \text{ kg}$$

Then with the Higgsmass $m_H \approx \frac{2,23}{10^{25}} \text{ kg}$ and $16! \approx 2,1 \times 10^{13}$ we find out that

$$m_H \approx m_\Lambda \cdot 16! \cdot 2,6336 \approx m_\Lambda \cdot 16! \cdot 4 \cdot \frac{\phi_{min}}{c}$$

If we can replace (assumption) the $\approx$ by $=$ then we can write

$$\frac{m_H}{4} = 16! \cdot m_\Lambda \cdot \frac{\phi_{min}}{c} \quad \begin{array}{l} \phi_{min} \dots \text{minimum of the potential} \\ \phi_{min} \approx 0,660464 \cdot c \quad c \dots \text{speed of light} \end{array}$$

With this assumption we can calculate the higgsmass. See Assumption 1 at the end.

Interpretationtrial for the factor 16!.

On the Oktoquintenfield we have 16 free degrees of freedom and on the Higgsfield we have 1 free degree of freedom to stimulate.

The 16 fields can be permutated so we can guess the factor 16! by this.

	OKTOQUINTENFIELD							HIGGSFIELD							
Φ_H															
Φ_G	1	i1	i2	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7							
Φ_R	1	i1	i2	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7							
Φ_F	1	i1	i2	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7							
Φ_S	1	i1	i2	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7							
Φ_O	1	i1	i2	i3	i4	i5	i6	i7							
	$\frac{1}{4} \cdot m_H$							$1 \cdot m_H$							

A second particle can be maybe found by the first term of the Octoquintenpotential.

Hint : The Higgsmass as calculated above comes from the second term of the Octoquintenpotential.

$$V(\phi) = \left(\frac{\Lambda \cdot c^4}{8\pi G}\right)^2 \cdot \left(-\frac{\varphi}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{|\phi|}{c}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{|\phi|}{c}\right)^4 - \frac{1}{2 \cdot \varphi^2} \cdot \left(\frac{|\phi|}{c}\right)^8 \right)$$

leads to

$$\frac{1}{4} \cdot m_H \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\varphi}{2}} \quad \frac{1}{4} \cdot m_H \quad \varphi \dots \text{golden ratio}$$

On the quadratic term we have the factor $\frac{\varphi}{2}$.

This gives us an energyrelation of $\frac{\frac{1}{4} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\varphi}{2}}}{1} \approx \frac{1}{4,44714376} \approx 0,22486$

The mass of the Higgsboson is $m_H \approx 125,18 \pm 0,16 \text{ GeV}$

The mass of the Oktoquintenboson then is $m_O \approx \frac{m_H}{4,44714376} \approx 28,1484 \text{ GeV}$

This is very near to the maybe found new particle on the LHC (<https://arxiv.org/abs/1808.01890>).

This is not a proof just a first idea for the new particle!

We will see if the new particle will be reconformed.

< 3.3 > Planck – Form

With the relation

$$P_p \cdot l_p^2 = \frac{c^4}{G}$$

we get from the Einstein – Form the Planck – Form of the OQP.

PLANCK – FORM

$$V(\phi) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{P_p}{2\pi}\right)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{\Lambda \cdot l_p^2 \cdot \varphi}{4}\right)^2 \cdot \left(- \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^2 + 2 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^4 - \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^8 \right)$$

where

$$P_p = \frac{c^7}{\hbar \cdot G^2} \quad \text{Planckpressure}$$

$$l_p^2 = \frac{\hbar \cdot G}{c^3} \quad \text{Plancklength}^2$$

$$\Lambda \cdot l_p^2 \approx \frac{2,8}{10^{122}} \approx \left(4 \cdot \frac{\phi_{\min}}{c \cdot \sqrt{\varphi}}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{48!^2} \quad \text{dimensionless}$$

This assumption $\approx \rightarrow =$ is backcalculated from the Combinatorial – Form of the Oktoquintenpotential which you can see later in this document.

On the combinatorial form the normalization factor N is very easy to explain and it leads to this assumption by going backward to the Planck – Form of the Oktoquintenpotential.

if $\Lambda \cdot l_p^2 \stackrel{\downarrow}{=} \left(4 \cdot \frac{\phi_{\min}}{c \cdot \sqrt{\varphi}}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{48!^2}$ then we can interprete

$$N = \frac{\phi_{\min}}{c} \cdot \frac{1}{48!} \quad \text{as normalization factor}$$

then our potential has the form

$$V(\phi) = \left(\frac{P_p}{2\pi}\right)^2 \cdot N^4 \cdot \left(- 8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^2 + 16 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^4 - 8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^8 \right)$$

For simplification we want to set $c = \hbar = G = 1$.

then the potential polynomial can be written in determinant form :

$$V(\phi) = 8 \cdot \left(\frac{\phi_{min}}{c} \frac{1}{48!} \right)^4 \cdot \begin{vmatrix} 1^2 & 1^2 & 0 & \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}} \right|^2 \\ 0 & \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}} \right|^2 & 0 & 1^2 \\ 0 & 0 & \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}} \right|^2 & 0 \\ \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}} \right|^2 & 1^2 & 0 & 1^2 \end{vmatrix}$$

with $\phi \in \mathbb{O}^6$

On this form we can see why the normalization factor has fourth potenz (4 × 4 matrix),

why $\frac{1}{48!}$

The Oktoquintenfield has $5 \times 8 = 40$ ϕ 's but the fifth chargeline is missing there.

Then if we add the fifth chargeline to the field we have 48 ϕ 's.

For every value of $|\phi|^2$ we can write

$$|\phi|^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{48} \phi_i^2 \quad \text{with } \phi_i \in \mathbb{R}$$

then for every permutation of the 48 degrees of freedom (coordinates) we get the same value for $|\phi|^2$.

That is why we have the factor $\frac{1}{48!}$ in the normalization factor N .

where

$$\phi_1 \dots \phi_8 = \phi_0^O \dots \phi_7^O \quad \text{and}$$

$$\phi_9 \dots \phi_{16} = \phi_0^S \dots \phi_7^S \quad \text{and}$$

$$\phi_{17} \dots \phi_{24} = \phi_0^F \dots \phi_7^F \quad \text{and}$$

$$\phi_{25} \dots \phi_{32} = \phi_0^R \dots \phi_7^R \quad \text{and}$$

$$\phi_{33} \dots \phi_{40} = \phi_0^G \dots \phi_7^G \quad \text{and}$$

$$\phi_{41} \dots \phi_{48} = \phi_0^H \dots \phi_7^H$$

S, F, R, G, H are the five senses – charges and O is no charge.

< 3.4 > Oktoquintenpotential and the 16 – Cell (Coxeter group B_4, D_4) :

As seen above we can write the potential very simple as a product of

$$V = \text{Normfactor} \times \text{Determinant}$$

The Determinant is like a higher dimensional "Volume".

In our case the dimension is 4.

Don't misunderstand "Volume" as real spacetimevolume.

It is similar to the Determinant in the Einstein Hilbert action.

Now we want to go TopDown and take a look on the 16-cell C_{16} .
 More details see here <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/16-cell>.

Some important known facts about the C_{16} .

- 1) count of cells = 16 tetrahedra
- 2) count of faces = 32 triangle
- 3) count of edges = 24
- 4) count of vertices = 8
- 5) every vertices has 6 edges
- 6) The Euler Characteristic of the 16-Cell is zero :
 $\chi = k_0 - k_1 + k_2 - k_3 = \#vertices - \#edges + \#faces - \#cells = 8 - 24 + 32 - 16 = 0$
- 7) The order of the automorphism group $S_2 \wr S_4$ is :
 $|Aut(C_{16})| = 2^4 \cdot 4! = 384$

How can we compare the 16-Cell with our Potential?

Es mentioned before our potential is like a 4-dimensional "volume".
 More exact it is a sum of 3 (4) volumes.

$$V(z) = \frac{N^4}{2} \cdot (0 \cdot z^0 - 16 \cdot z^1 + 32 \cdot z^2 - 16 \cdot z^4)$$

where $z = \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^2$ and
 $c = G = h = 1$

To make the potential zero we set $z = 1$ or equivalent $\phi = \sqrt{\varphi}$

$$V(1) = \frac{N^4}{2} \cdot (0 \cdot 1^0 - 16 \cdot 1^1 + 32 \cdot 1^2 - 16 \cdot 1^4) = 0$$

$\begin{matrix} \text{vertices} & \text{edges} & \text{faces} & \text{cells} \end{matrix}$

$$\chi = k_0 - k_1 + k_2 - k_3 = 8 - 24 + 32 - 16 = 0 \text{ Euler-Characteristic}$$

we can see that both formulars alternate
 and if we draw out 16 we get for the potential

$$V(1) = N^4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot (-16 \cdot 1^1 + 32 \cdot 1^2 - 16 \cdot 1^4)$$

$\begin{matrix} | & | & | \\ \text{8-24} & + & 32 & - & 16 \\ \text{vertices} & \text{edges} & \text{faces} & & \text{cells} \end{matrix}$

We have two disagreements

- 1) we have no vertices in the potential.
 The vertices are added to the edges!
- 2) The power of the 1 which should be the dimension of the object
 does fit for the edges and the faces but not for the cells!

to 1)
 How can we annihilate the vertices?
 Answer : we replace it by a loop (string) and get a closed edge.
 We can interpret this loops as particles.

or

to 2)
 the cells can be easily extended to fourth dimension on a convex graph.
 2 – dimension example :

So finally the potential shows 1 – dimensional , 2 – dimensional and 4 – dimensional stimulated objects.

Interpretation :
 1 – dimension objects are particles
 We have two types of 1 – dimensional object.
 Closed and open ones.

$$\begin{matrix} 8 - 24 & + & 32 & - & 16 \\ \text{edges} & & \text{faces} & & \text{cells} \end{matrix}$$

$$V(1) = N^4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot (-16 \cdot 1^1 + 32 \cdot 1^2 - 16 \cdot 1^4)$$

With the other zero point ($\phi = c$) we can create the same particle graph C_{16} .
 z then is $\frac{1}{\phi}$

$$V(z) = V\left(\frac{1}{\phi}\right) = N^4 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(-16 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\phi}\right)^1 + 32 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\phi}\right)^2 - 16 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\phi}\right)^4\right)$$

< 3.5 > Combinatorial – Form

We have the strange factor $\frac{1}{2}$ in front of the bracket.
 How can we interpret this factor?

We can draw this factor inside the brackets and set finally

$$N = \frac{\phi_{min}}{c} \cdot \frac{1}{48!} \quad \text{then we get finally the}$$

COMBINATORIAL – FORM

$$V(\phi) = N^4 \cdot \left(-8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}} \right|^2 + 16 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}} \right|^4 - 8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\phi}} \right|^8 \right)$$

for the potential.

In mathematics this is called a generating function.

This shows that the interval $[0, \phi_{\min}]$ can be divided in $48!$ - intervals $[0, N \cdot c] + (N \cdot c, 2 \cdot N \cdot c] + \dots$

Deduction of the fundamental equation see APPENDIX III.

2) the red **8** (edges).

As seen above the 8 comes from $-8 = 4 - 12$.

4 particles in the diagonal
 12 particles } zero curvature tensor

3) the blue **16** (faces).

This is the count of the $16 = 4 + 2.6$ fields of the first curvature tensor ($\approx$ metric tensor). } in the diagonal

4) the green **8** (cells).

This is the count of the $8 = 2 + 2.3$ fields of the second curvature tensor ($\approx$ spinmetric tensor). } in the diagonal

Details to this curvature tensors see later.

Another interesting coincidence is the mass in the (visible) universe and the permutations of the $\mathbb{O}^6$ - field ($48! \approx 1,2414 \times 10^{61}$).

If the universe is a statistical combinatorial universe then what in this universe can be differentiated?

In case of finit groups this are the permutations.

In our definition field $\mathbb{O}^6$ we have $48!$ permutations of the coordinates.

Now what can this permutations be?

What finit objects do we know in our universe?

At last only Particles.

Sounds strange but can we identify one such permutation with a special particle?

I think yes.

Let us think that every single $SU(5)$ W and Z Bosen is such a permutation with mass = planckmass = $1,2211 \times 10^{19}$ GeV.

Then mass in the universe = $\frac{48!}{2} \times$ Planckmass

$$= \frac{1}{2} \times 1,2414 \times 10^{61} \times 1,2211 \times 10^{19} \text{ GeV} \approx 0,75 \times 10^{80} \text{ GeV}$$

The factor $\frac{1}{2}$ because also the antiparticles are counted in $48!$

This is in accordance with other calculations.

< 4 > Lagrangendensity of the Octoquintenfield/Octoquintenpotential

Hint :

I do the same steps as shown in this cooking recipe for the Higgsfield.

<https://www.lsw.uni-heidelberg.de/users/mcamenzi/HDHiggs.pdf>

splitting of the Oktoquintenfield

Similar to the SU(3) Vectorbosons which are named Gluons we name our SU(5) Tensorbosons Repelions.

The force between different charged Repelions is repulsiv because they are tensorbosons (2nd – order).

Similar to the Higgsfield we assign our Repelions to the Oktoquintenfield by the following scheme.

The numbers are the sense charges (see < 2 >).

- 5 = See
- 4 = Feeling
- 3 = Smelling
- 2 = Taste
- 1 = Hear

$$massrelation = \frac{visible\ matter}{dark\ matter} = \frac{1}{5}$$

similar to the the higgsfield where the vacuumexpectation is

$$\phi_{vac} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ v \end{pmatrix}$$

the vacuumexpectation of the Oktoquintenfield is (green, yellow, orange)

$$\phi_{vac} = v \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 0 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \\ 1 + 0 + i_2 + i_3 \\ 1 + i_1 + 0 + i_3 \\ 1 + i_1 + i_2 + 0 \\ 1 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

where v = e1 ist the minimum of the Oktoquintenpotential and i1, i2 and i3 the imaginaer quaternions.

As mentioned in above we assume that the left 4 charged bosons decomposed to electrons, neutrinos and quarks and couple to the higgs field instead. Then the vacuum expectation changes to :

$$\phi_{vac} = v. \begin{pmatrix} 1 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \\ 1 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

STEP 1 : Lorentzinvariant Lagrangedensity for the Octoquintenfield

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi = (D^\mu \phi)^\dagger (D_\mu \phi) - V(\phi^\dagger \phi)$$

with $\phi \in \mathbb{O}^5$ Octonions⁵

The potential V is shown in < 3 >

$\mathcal{T}_{ij}$ $j \rightarrow$	Generators of the $SU(5)$				
$i \downarrow$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & i & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$
	$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$	$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$	

$W -$ Boson scheme

$$\begin{pmatrix} W^{11} & W^{12} & W^{13} & W^{14} & W^{15} \\ W^{21} & W^{22} & W^{23} & W^{24} & W^{25} \\ W^{31} & W^{32} & W^{33} & W^{34} & W^{35} \\ W^{41} & W^{42} & W^{43} & W^{44} & W^{45} \\ W^{51} & W^{52} & W^{53} & W^{54} & \end{pmatrix}$$

hint : $W^{ij} = W_\mu^{ij}$

We take a look on the symmetry

$$SU(5) \times U(1) \times U(1)$$

$$W^{ij} \quad B^0 \quad B^1$$

calculate covariant derivation

$$D_\mu \phi = (\partial_\mu + \frac{i.g}{2} \cdot \tau_{ij} \cdot W_\mu^{ij} + \frac{i.g'}{2} \cdot Id^0 B_\mu^0 + \frac{i.g''}{2} \cdot Id^1 B_\mu^1) \cdot \phi$$

$$\tau_{ij} \cdot W_\mu^{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} W^{51} & | & W^{11} - i \cdot W^{12} & | & W^{21} - i \cdot W^{23} & | & W^{31} - i \cdot W^{34} & | & W^{41} - i \cdot W^{45} \\ \hline W^{11} + i \cdot W^{12} & & W^{52} & & W^{22} - i \cdot W^{13} & & W^{14} - i \cdot W^{32} & & W^{15} - i \cdot W^{42} \\ W^{21} + i \cdot W^{23} & & W^{22} + i \cdot W^{13} & & W^{53} & & W^{24} - i \cdot W^{33} & & W^{25} - i \cdot W^{43} \\ \hline W^{31} + i \cdot W^{34} & & W^{14} + i \cdot W^{32} & & W^{24} + i \cdot W^{33} & & W^{54} & & W^{35} - i \cdot W^{44} \\ \hline W^{41} + i \cdot W^{45} & & W^{15} + i \cdot W^{42} & & W^{25} + i \cdot W^{43} & & W^{35} + i \cdot W^{44} & & -(W^{51} + W^{52} + W^{53} + W^{54}) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$Id^0 = Id^1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

and for example

$$W_{12} = \frac{W^{11} - i.W^{12}}{\sqrt{2}}$$

The boson which changes the charge from 1 (hear) to 2 (taste).

Then

$$D_\mu \phi_{vac} = \frac{v}{2} \cdot i \cdot g \cdot \begin{pmatrix} W^{51} & \sqrt{2} W_{12} & \sqrt{2} W_{13} & \sqrt{2} W_{14} & \sqrt{2} W_{15} \\ \sqrt{2} W_{21} & W^{52} & \sqrt{2} W_{23} & \sqrt{2} W_{24} & \sqrt{2} W_{25} \\ \sqrt{2} W_{31} & \sqrt{2} W_{32} & W^{53} & \sqrt{2} W_{34} & \sqrt{2} W_{35} \\ \sqrt{2} W_{41} & \sqrt{2} W_{42} & \sqrt{2} W_{43} & W^{54} & \sqrt{2} W_{45} \\ \sqrt{2} W_{51} & \sqrt{2} W_{52} & \sqrt{2} W_{53} & \sqrt{2} W_{54} & -(W^{51} + W^{52} + W^{53} + W^{54}) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \\ 1 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$+ \frac{v}{2} \cdot i \cdot \begin{pmatrix} g'.B^0 + g''.B^1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & g'.B^0 + g''.B^1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & g'.B^0 + g''.B^1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & g'.B^0 + g''.B^1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & g'.B^0 + g''.B^1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & g'.B^0 + g''.B^1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \\ 1 + i_1 + i_2 + i_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

then

$$(D^\mu \phi_{vac})^\dagger (D_\mu \phi_{vac}) = \frac{v^2}{4} \cdot \left[\begin{array}{l} 4 \cdot (gW^{51} + g'.B^0 + g''.B^1)^2 + 8g^2 \cdot (W_{12}W_{21} + W_{13}W_{31} + W_{14}W_{41} + W_{15}W_{51}) + \text{something} + \\ 4 \cdot (gW^{52} + g'.B^0 + g''.B^1)^2 + 8g^2 \cdot (W_{12}W_{21} + W_{23}W_{32} + W_{24}W_{42} + W_{25}W_{52}) + \text{something} + \\ 4 \cdot (gW^{53} + g'.B^0 + g''.B^1)^2 + 8g^2 \cdot (W_{13}W_{31} + W_{23}W_{32} + W_{34}W_{43} + W_{35}W_{53}) + \text{something} + \\ 4 \cdot (gW^{54} + g'.B^0 + g''.B^1)^2 + 8g^2 \cdot (W_{14}W_{41} + W_{24}W_{42} + W_{34}W_{43} + W_{45}W_{54}) + \text{something} + \\ 4 \cdot (-g(W^{51} + W^{52} + W^{53} + W^{54}) + g'.B^0 + g''.B^1)^2 + 8g^2 \cdot (W_{15}W_{51} + W_{25}W_{52} + W_{35}W_{53} + W_{45}W_{54}) \end{array} \right]$$

hint : $W^{ij} = W_\mu^{ij}$ and $B^0 = B_\mu^0$ and $B^1 = B_\mu^1$

like the result of the Higgsfield we expect something like that :

$$(D^\mu \phi_{vac})^\dagger (D_\mu \phi_{vac}) = \frac{v^2}{8} \cdot (g^2 \cdot (W^+)^2 + g^2 \cdot (W^-)^2 + (g^2 + g'^2) \cdot Z_\mu \cdot Z^\mu + 0 \cdot A_\mu \cdot A^\mu)$$

We have a lot of summands so we first want to take a look on the diagonal elements of the covariant derivation.

In the Higgsfieldtheory we get as result the massive Z – Bosons and the Photon as a mixing of neutral W and B bosons.

We calculate the expression which is a symmetric bilinear form :

Momentumdensity – Matrix

$$(W^{51} \ W^{52} \ W^{53} \ W^{54} \ B^0 \ B^1) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 8g^2 & 4g^2 & 4g^2 & 4g^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 4g^2 & 8g^2 & 4g^2 & 4g^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 4g^2 & 4g^2 & 8g^2 & 4g^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 4g^2 & 4g^2 & 4g^2 & 8g^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 20g'^2 & 20g' \cdot g'' \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 20g' \cdot g'' & 20g''^2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} W^{51} \\ W^{52} \\ W^{53} \\ W^{54} \\ B^0 \\ B^1 \end{pmatrix}$$

linearly independent linearly dependent

and compare it with the red area of the dynamic lagrangepart.

Someone can easy proof that is identical.

Then with diagonalizing the Momentumdensity – Matrix we get the following result :

$$(D^\mu \phi_{vac})^\dagger (D_\mu \phi_{vac}) = \frac{v^2}{4} \cdot [\text{green area} + \text{red area} + \text{something}] = 0$$

$$(D^\mu \phi_{vac})^\dagger (D_\mu \phi_{vac}) = \frac{v^2}{4} \cdot [8g^2 \cdot (|W_{12}|^2 + |W_{21}|^2 + |W_{13}|^2 + |W_{31}|^2 + |W_{14}|^2 + |W_{41}|^2 + |W_{23}|^2 + |W_{32}|^2 + |W_{24}|^2 + |W_{42}|^2 + |W_{34}|^2 + |W_{43}|^2 + |W_{15}|^2 + |W_{51}|^2 + |W_{35}|^2 + |W_{53}|^2 + |W_{25}|^2 + |W_{52}|^2 + |W_{45}|^2 + |W_{54}|^2) + 8g^2 \cdot (|Z^0|^2 + |Z^1|^2 + |Z^2|^2 + |Z^3|^2) + 20 \cdot (g'^2 + g''^2) \cdot |\Lambda|^2 + \frac{0}{2} |G|^2]$$

U(1) Gravitation field

eigenvalues of the Momentumdensity matrix

Momentumdensity Quadrats

The couplingangle α comes from the Extremalpoint of the Oktoquintenpotential.
 As calculated in < 8 > we have :

Mixingangles

$$\theta_W \approx \alpha_1 \approx 28,89^\circ \quad (\theta_W = \text{Weinbergangle})$$

$$\theta_K = 28,89^\circ$$

direct connection between OQP and couplings.

$\theta_K = \alpha_{min} \approx 28,9^\circ$
 c ...speed of light
 φ ...golden ratio

$$\theta_P = \alpha_{max} \approx 121,6^\circ$$

Then the Graviton and the Λ – Boson is a mixing :

$$\begin{pmatrix} \Lambda_\mu \\ G_\mu \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta_K) & -\sin(\theta_K) \\ \sin(\theta_K) & \cos(\theta_K) \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} B_\mu^0 \\ B_\mu^1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The Impulsdensity and therefore the massdensity and therefore the mass of the W and Z Bosons are equal because they have the same couplingconstant g.

< 5 > Curvaturetensors by the Octoquintenfield

We allow $\phi \in \mathbb{C}$

The construction comes from multiplications (symmetric to the diagonal) by 2 degrees of freedom (complex subspaces).
With this construction the tensor is symmetric in the diagonal.

$$\phi = \begin{bmatrix} \phi^G \\ \phi^R \\ \phi^F \\ \phi^S \\ \phi^O \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_0^G + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^G + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^G + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^G + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^G + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^G + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^G + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^G \\ \phi_0^R + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^R + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^R + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^R + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^R + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^R + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^R + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^R \\ \phi_0^F + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^F + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^F + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^F + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^F + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^F + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^F + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^F \\ \phi_0^S + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^S + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^S + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^S + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^S + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^S + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^S + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^S \\ \phi_0^O + i_1 \cdot \phi_1^O + i_2 \cdot \phi_2^O + i_3 \cdot \phi_3^O + i_4 \cdot \phi_4^O + i_5 \cdot \phi_5^O + i_6 \cdot \phi_6^O + i_7 \cdot \phi_7^O \end{bmatrix}$$

ΦG	1	i_1	i_2	i_3	i_4	i_5	i_6	i_7
ΦR	i_1	1	i_2	i_3	i_4	i_5	i_6	i_7
ΦF	i_2	i_1	1	i_3	i_4	i_5	i_6	i_7
ΦS	i_3	i_2	i_1	1	i_4	i_5	i_6	i_7
ΦO	i_4	i_3	i_2	i_1	1	i_5	i_6	i_7

Charge 0

$c \dots \text{speed of light}$
 $G \dots \text{Gravitationconstant}$
 $\hbar \dots \text{Planckconstant}$

symmetric Curvature Tensor

$$C_{em} = \frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \phi_0^O \cdot \phi_0^O & i_1 \cdot \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G & i_2 \cdot \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G & i_3 \cdot \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \\ i_1 \cdot \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G & -\phi_1^O \cdot \phi_1^O & i_3 \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R & -i_2 \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R \\ i_2 \cdot \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G & i_3 \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R & -\phi_2^O \cdot \phi_2^O & i_1 \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F \\ i_3 \cdot \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G & -i_2 \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R & i_1 \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F & -\phi_3^O \cdot \phi_3^O \end{bmatrix}$$

10 independent fields.

remark :

for $\phi = c$ we get as curvature the plank curvature which is the reciprocal of the plank area.

The value of the curvature is :

$$0,34 \times 10^{70} \frac{1}{m^2}$$

Second CURVATURE TENSOR from the Octoquintenfield (generates a spinpotential)

The construction comes from multiplications by 4 degrees of freedom (quaternionic subspaces). With this construction the tensor is symmetric in both diagonals.

$$\phi = \begin{bmatrix} \phi^G \\ \phi^R \\ \phi^F \\ \phi^S \\ \phi^O \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \phi_0^G + i_1 \phi_1^G + i_2 \phi_2^G + i_3 \phi_3^G + i_4 \phi_4^G + i_5 \phi_5^G + i_6 \phi_6^G + i_7 \phi_7^G \\ \phi_0^R + i_1 \phi_1^R + i_2 \phi_2^R + i_3 \phi_3^R + i_4 \phi_4^R + i_5 \phi_5^R + i_6 \phi_6^R + i_7 \phi_7^R \\ \phi_0^F + i_1 \phi_1^F + i_2 \phi_2^F + i_3 \phi_3^F + i_4 \phi_4^F + i_5 \phi_5^F + i_6 \phi_6^F + i_7 \phi_7^F \\ \phi_0^S + i_1 \phi_1^S + i_2 \phi_2^S + i_3 \phi_3^S + i_4 \phi_4^S + i_5 \phi_5^S + i_6 \phi_6^S + i_7 \phi_7^S \\ \phi_0^O + i_1 \phi_1^O + i_2 \phi_2^O + i_3 \phi_3^O + i_4 \phi_4^O + i_5 \phi_5^O + i_6 \phi_6^O + i_7 \phi_7^O \end{bmatrix}$$

$$C_{spin} = \left(\frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar}\right)^2 \cdot \begin{bmatrix} -\phi_0^O \cdot \phi_0^O \cdot \phi_3^O \cdot \phi_3^O & -C & B & -A \\ -C & \phi_1^O \cdot \phi_1^O \cdot \phi_2^O \cdot \phi_2^O & -A & B \\ B & -A & \phi_1^O \cdot \phi_1^O \cdot \phi_2^O \cdot \phi_2^O & -C \\ -A & B & -C & -\phi_0^O \cdot \phi_0^O \cdot \phi_3^O \cdot \phi_3^O \end{bmatrix}$$

$$A = \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R \quad B = \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R \quad C = \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F$$

5 independent fields A, B, C and two in the diagonal (blue and yellow).

So finally we get three derivation – or curvature tensors of the Octoquintenpotential for twisted spacetime excitation

0-th Curvaturetensor

ϕ_0^O	$i_1 \cdot \phi_1^G$	$i_2 \cdot \phi_2^G$	$i_3 \cdot \phi_3^G$
ϕ_0^R	$i_1 \cdot \phi_1^O$	$i_2 \cdot \phi_2^R$	$i_3 \cdot \phi_3^R$
ϕ_0^F	$i_1 \cdot \phi_1^F$	$i_2 \cdot \phi_2^O$	$i_3 \cdot \phi_3^F$
ϕ_0^S	$i_1 \cdot \phi_1^S$	$i_2 \cdot \phi_2^S$	$i_3 \cdot \phi_3^O$

ϕ_i unit is speed m/s

1-Curvaturetensor Cem em = energy-momentum

$\phi_0^O \cdot \phi_0^O$	$i_1 \cdot \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G$	$i_2 \cdot \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G$	$i_3 \cdot \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G$
$i_1 \cdot \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G$	$-\phi_1^O \cdot \phi_1^O$	$i_3 \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R$	$-i_2 \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R$
$i_2 \cdot \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G$	$i_3 \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R$	$-\phi_2^O \cdot \phi_2^O$	$i_1 \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F$
$i_3 \cdot \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G$	$-i_2 \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R$	$i_1 \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F$	$-\phi_3^O \cdot \phi_3^O$

This tensor is up to a constant equal to the energy-momentum tensor.

Energydensity :

$$\frac{E_{i,j}}{m^3} = \phi_i \cdot \phi_j \cdot \frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar} \cdot \frac{c^4}{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G} = \phi_i \cdot \phi_j \cdot \frac{c^2}{K \cdot l_p^2}$$

c ...speed of light

G ...Gravitationconstant

$\hbar$...Planckconstant

K ...Einsteinconstant

l_p^2 ...Planckarea

the vacuumexcitation :

$$\phi_i^2 = \Lambda \cdot \frac{G \cdot \hbar}{c} \quad i = 0, 1, 2, 3$$

responsible for $SO(1,3)$ symmetry

2-Curvaturetensor Cspin

$-C$	B	$-A$	
$-C$	$-A$	B	
B	$-A$	$-C$	
$-A$	B	$-C$	

$$= -\phi_0^O \cdot \phi_0^O \cdot \phi_3^O \cdot \phi_3^O$$

$$= \phi_1^O \cdot \phi_1^O \cdot \phi_2^O \cdot \phi_2^O$$

$$A = \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R$$

$$B = \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R$$

$$C = \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F$$

responsible for $SU(2)$ symmetry

< 6 > Extension of the General Relativity GR by the second curvaturetensor

The Octoquintenpotential has two symmetric curvaturetensors.

This motivates us to extend the Einstein Equation.

I think this shows that the GR (General Relativity) has to be extended

by an imaginry part (spinpart) to be a consistent quantumtheorie.

So finally we expect something like $GR+i \cdot GR^0$ where GR^0 is the spinpart.

with the two curvature tensors C_{em} and C_{spin} we can define following equation :

EGR Extended General Relativity

$$g \cdot \text{Real}(C_{em}) + g^2 \cdot \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot C_{spin} = \frac{8\pi \cdot G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu})$$

where the real part is the GR and the imaginaer part is GR^O

GR...General Relativity

GR^O ...Spinextension of GR

φ ...golden ratio

Λ ...cosmological constant

l_p ...Plancklength

$$g = \begin{cases} \Lambda \cdot l_p^2 \approx \frac{2,8}{10^{122}} \text{ for the vacuum} \\ 1 \text{ else} \end{cases}$$

Hint :

The small value of g shows the cosmological constant problem or vacuum catastrophe.

$$g = \Lambda \cdot l_p^2 \approx \frac{2,8}{10^{122}} \text{ for the vacuum}$$

the operator $\text{Real}(A)$ is defined by

$$\text{Real} \left(\begin{pmatrix} a_{0,0} & i_1 \cdot a_{0,1} & i_2 \cdot a_{0,2} & i_3 \cdot a_{0,3} \\ i_1 \cdot a_{1,0} & a_{1,1} & i_3 \cdot a_{1,2} & i_2 \cdot a_{1,3} \\ i_2 \cdot a_{2,0} & i_3 \cdot a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & i_1 \cdot a_{2,3} \\ i_3 \cdot a_{3,0} & i_2 \cdot a_{3,1} & i_1 \cdot a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} \right) = \begin{pmatrix} a_{0,0} & a_{0,1} & a_{0,2} & a_{0,3} \\ a_{1,0} & a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} \\ a_{2,0} & a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} \\ a_{3,0} & a_{3,1} & a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix}$$

the reversing Real^{-1} is :

$$\text{Real}^{-1} \left(\begin{pmatrix} a_{0,0} & a_{0,1} & a_{0,2} & a_{0,3} \\ a_{1,0} & a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} \\ a_{2,0} & a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} \\ a_{3,0} & a_{3,1} & a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} \right) = \begin{pmatrix} a_{0,0} & i_1 \cdot a_{0,1} & i_2 \cdot a_{0,2} & i_3 \cdot a_{0,3} \\ i_1 \cdot a_{1,0} & a_{1,1} & i_3 \cdot a_{1,2} & i_2 \cdot a_{1,3} \\ i_2 \cdot a_{2,0} & i_3 \cdot a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & i_1 \cdot a_{2,3} \\ i_3 \cdot a_{3,0} & i_2 \cdot a_{3,1} & i_1 \cdot a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix}$$

i_1, i_2, i_3 ...imaginaer quaternions

more detailed with the two curvature tensors of the Octoquinten field :

$$\frac{8\pi \cdot G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = g \cdot \text{Real}(C_{em}) + g^2 \cdot \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot C_{spin} =$$

$$= \frac{g \cdot c}{G \cdot \hbar} \cdot \left[\begin{pmatrix} \phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_0^0 & \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G & \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G & \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \\ \text{sym.} & -\phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_1^0 & \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R & -\phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & -\phi_2^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 & \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & -\phi_3^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 \end{pmatrix} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{g \cdot c}{\Lambda \cdot G \cdot \hbar} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -\phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 - \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F & \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R - \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R \\ \text{sym.} & \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 - \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R & \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R - \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 - \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & -\phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 \end{pmatrix} \right]$$

10 different products

5 different products

sym. and the red products are redundant

generates Poincare group $\mathbb{R}^{1,3} \rtimes O(1,3)$

$2 \times S^1 \times S^1 \times SU(2) = 2 \times \mathbb{T}^2 \times SU(2)$ with $\mathbb{T}^2 = \text{Torus}$

$\mathbb{T}^2$...Clifford – Torus

This flat torus is a subset of the unit 3 – sphere S^3 .

The Clifford torus divides the 3 – sphere into two congruent solid tori.

The Clifford – Torus embedded in S^3 becomes a minimal surface.

The second curvature tensor C_{spin} is determined by the first curvature tensor C_{em} because its components are a mix of the components of C_{em} .

< 6.1 > The vacuum part of the extended Einstein equation then is :

with

$$\phi_0^0 = \phi_1^0 = \phi_2^0 = \phi_3^0 = c \quad \text{speed of light and other } \phi^i \text{ are zero and}$$

$$g = \Lambda \cdot l_p^2 \quad \text{for the vacuum}$$

then

$$\text{Vacuum Energydensity} = \frac{c^4}{8\pi G} \cdot [\Lambda \cdot \begin{matrix} \text{hyperbolic (1,3)} \\ \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \Lambda \cdot \begin{matrix} \text{ultrahyperbolic (2,2)} \\ \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}] \begin{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} \oplus \\ \oplus \\ \oplus \\ \oplus \end{pmatrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} \oplus \\ \oplus \\ \oplus \\ \oplus \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix} \begin{matrix} \mathbb{T}_{\text{up}}^2 \\ \mathbb{T}_{\text{down}}^2 \end{matrix}$$

$\mathbb{T}_{\Lambda^0}^2 = \begin{pmatrix} \ominus \\ \oplus \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} C_- \\ C_+ \end{pmatrix}$
 Spinor

generates flat expanding spacetime

generates 2 × spinning Torus $\mathbb{T}_{\Lambda^0}^2 = S^1 \times S^1$

flat Clifford – Torus

generates flat expanding and twisting vacuum

This is in accordance with the Oktoquinten – Potential on $\phi = c$

$$V(c) = \left(\frac{\Lambda \cdot c^4}{8\pi G}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{2 \cdot \varphi^2} \cdot \left(-\varphi^3 + 2 \cdot \varphi^2 - 1 \right) = \text{Energydensity}^2 = 0$$

$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$

$\frac{i\Lambda}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$

< 6.2 > Scalefactor for the accelerated expanding Universe by our assumption

To make it simple we are thinking about an universe without radiation and mass.
 This means only the vacuumenergydensity is acting.
 Then the Hubbleconstant is really constant.

$$H = \sqrt{\frac{c^2 \cdot \Lambda}{3}} = \frac{a'(t)}{a(t)} \quad \text{then}$$

$$a(t) \propto e^{H \cdot t} = e^{\sqrt{\frac{c^2 \cdot \Lambda}{3}} \cdot t}$$

then with assumption $\Lambda \cdot l_p^2 = \left(4 \cdot \frac{\phi_{\min}}{c \cdot \sqrt{\varphi}}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{48!^2}$

we get finally

$$a(t) \propto e^{H \cdot t} = e^{\sqrt{\frac{2^2}{3^3} \cdot \frac{4 \cdot \sin(\alpha_{\min})}{48!}} \cdot \frac{t}{t_p}}$$

- a...scale factor
- Λ...cosmological constant
- c...speed of light
- l_p ...Plancklength
- t_p ...Plancktime
- $\phi_{\min}$...minimum in the Oktoquintenpotential
- $\alpha_{\min}$... see < 8 > at the end of the document.

< 7 > Getting a closed form for the Extended General Relativity EGR.

we know that our energy – momentum curvature tensor

$$\text{Real}(C_{em}) = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{R}{2} \cdot g_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda \cdot g_{\mu\nu} \quad \text{and that}$$

C_{spin} is defined by multiplication of tensorelements of C_{em}

The question now is how can we express C_{spin} analogous to C_{em} above as terms of Riemann – Geometrie?

For that we define the operator for 4×4 matrices or tensors :

Matrixoperator Tau

$$\overline{A} = T + \diagdown + \diagup$$

Transpose
in the big diagonal from top right to bottom left.
and then in the small diagonals

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{0,0} & a_{0,1} & a_{0,2} & a_{0,3} \\ a_{1,0} & a_{1,1} & a_{1,2} & a_{1,3} \\ a_{2,0} & a_{2,1} & a_{2,2} & a_{2,3} \\ a_{3,0} & a_{3,1} & a_{3,2} & a_{3,3} \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} a_{3,3} & a_{2,3} & a_{1,3} & a_{0,3} \\ a_{3,2} & a_{2,2} & a_{1,2} & a_{0,2} \\ a_{3,1} & a_{2,1} & a_{1,1} & a_{0,1} \\ a_{3,0} & a_{2,0} & a_{1,0} & a_{0,0} \end{pmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} a_{3,3} & a_{2,3} & a_{1,3} & a_{1,2} \\ a_{3,2} & a_{2,2} & a_{0,3} & a_{0,2} \\ a_{3,1} & a_{3,0} & a_{1,1} & a_{0,1} \\ a_{2,1} & a_{2,0} & a_{1,0} & a_{0,0} \end{pmatrix}$$

A $A^{\overline{}}$

and a

special simple matricesmultiplication

$$C = A \cdot B$$

with

$$c_{i,j} = \begin{cases} +a_{i,j} \cdot b_{i,j} & \text{if } i = j \\ -a_{i,j} \cdot b_{i,j} & \text{if } i \neq j \end{cases}$$

then it is easy to see that

$$(A + B)^{\overline{}} = A^{\overline{}} + B^{\overline{}}$$

$$(A^{\overline{}})^{\overline{}} = A$$

with

$$C_{em} = \frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_0^0 & i_1 \cdot \phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G & i_2 \cdot \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G & i_3 \cdot \phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \\ \text{sym.} & -\phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_1^0 & i_3 \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R & -i_2 \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & -\phi_2^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 & i_1 \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & -\phi_3^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 \end{pmatrix} = \frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar} \cdot V_{em}$$

and

$$C_{spin} = \left(\frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar}\right)^2 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -\phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_0^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 \cdot \phi_3^0 & -\phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F & \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R & -\phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R \\ \text{sym.} & \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 & -\phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R & \phi_0^F \cdot \phi_2^G \cdot \phi_1^S \cdot \phi_3^R \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_1^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 \cdot \phi_2^0 & -\phi_0^R \cdot \phi_1^G \cdot \phi_2^S \cdot \phi_3^F \\ \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & \text{sym.} & -\phi_0^S \cdot \phi_3^G \cdot \phi_1^F \cdot \phi_2^R \end{pmatrix} = \left(\frac{c}{G \cdot \hbar}\right)^2 \cdot V_{spin}$$

it follows that

$$C_{spin} = \text{Real}(C_{em}) \cdot \text{Real}(C_{em})^{\overline{}}$$

with

$$\text{Real}(C_{em}) = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{R}{2} \cdot g_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda \cdot g_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda \cdot g_{\mu\nu} = K_{\mu\nu}$$

and

$$\text{Real}(C_{em}) + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot C_{spin} = \frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu})$$

we get the final compact result for the extension of General Relativity by

EGR

$$K_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot K_{\mu\nu} \cdot K_{\mu\nu}^{\mathfrak{F}} = \frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu})$$

with

$$S_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot T_{\mu\nu} \cdot T_{\mu\nu}^{\mathfrak{F}} \dots \text{Spintensor}$$

$$K_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{R}{2} \cdot g_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda \cdot g_{\mu\nu}$$

$$K_{\mu\nu}^{\mathfrak{F}} = R_{\mu\nu}^{\mathfrak{F}} - \frac{R}{2} \cdot g_{\mu\nu}^{\mathfrak{F}} + \Lambda \cdot g_{\mu\nu}^{\mathfrak{F}}$$

φ ...golden ratio

The real part is the known General Relativity.

The imaginaer part is the Spinextension of GR.

Hint : The Energy–Stress tensor is still symmetric with or without Spin!

< 7.1 > Showing a combinatorial dimensionless form of the EGR

With the relation shown in < 3.5 > and Appendix III

$$\Lambda \cdot l_p^2 = \frac{1}{\varphi} \cdot (4v)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{48!^2} \quad \text{with } v = \frac{\phi_{min}}{c}$$

we can write :

$$\frac{1}{\Lambda} = l_p^2 \cdot \varphi \cdot \frac{48!^2}{(4v)^2}$$

Then our formular in < 6 > can be written to :

$$\frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = g \cdot \text{Real}(C_{em}) + g^2 \cdot \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot C_{spin} \quad g = \begin{cases} \Lambda \cdot l_p^2 & \text{for the vacuum} \\ 1 & \text{else} \end{cases}$$

Hint : instead of $\text{Real}(C_{em})$ we write short C_{em} and keep it in mind!

$$\frac{8 \cdot \pi \cdot G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = g \cdot C_{em} + g^2 \cdot \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot l_p^2 \cdot \frac{48!^2}{(4v)^2} \cdot C_{spin}$$

$$\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = g \cdot \frac{c}{G\hbar} \cdot V_{em} + g^2 \cdot \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot l_p^2 \cdot \frac{48!^2}{(4v)^2} \cdot (\frac{c}{G\hbar})^2 \cdot V_{spin}$$

then with

$$\frac{c}{G\hbar} = \frac{1}{c^2 \cdot l_p^2}$$

$$\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = g \cdot \frac{1}{c^2 \cdot l_p^2} \cdot V_{em} + g^2 \cdot \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{48!^2}{(4v)^2} \cdot \frac{1}{c^4 \cdot l_p^2} \cdot V_{spin} \quad | \cdot l_p^2$$

$$\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \cdot l_p^2 \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = g \cdot \frac{1}{c^2} \cdot V_{em} + g^2 \cdot \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{48!^2}{(4v)^2} \cdot \frac{1}{c^4} \cdot V_{spin}$$

then with

$$P_p = \frac{c^7}{G^2 \cdot \hbar} \quad \text{Planckpressure and } g = 1 \text{ for not vacuum}$$

we get finally

$$\boxed{\frac{8\pi}{P_p} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = \frac{1}{c^2} \cdot V_{em} + \frac{i}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{16N^2} \cdot \frac{1}{c^4} \cdot V_{spin}}$$

V_{em}, V_{spin} see < 7 >
 $N = \frac{v}{48!}$

dimensionless Combinatorial – Form of the EGR

< 7.2 > Spin and possible proofing of the Extended General Relativity EGR.

As noted in < 5 > the second curvaturetensor C_{spin} is responsible for the Spin.

Obviously the C_{spin} is directly connected to the energy – momentum curvaturetensor C_{em} .

So in principle the Extended General Relativity short EGR could be proofed because the spin of a particle changes the Energy – Momentum – Tensor.

First we have to show how the spin of a particle acts on the C_{spin} .

For that we have to take a closer look on the C_{spin} .

As seen in < 5 > the structure is :

Now how can we embed dirac – fermions with spin $\frac{1}{2}$ into the EGR?

For that we want to assign the structure of the C_{spin} in the following way to fermions :

Then a resting electron excites the C_{spin} and the C_{em} as follow :

$$Spin = \frac{1}{2} \text{ Dirac: } \begin{array}{c} +\frac{1}{2} \\ \begin{array}{|c|c|c|c|} \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \end{array} \\ -\frac{1}{2} \\ \color{red}\blacksquare \text{ excited components} \end{array} = \begin{pmatrix} -\phi_0^{0^2}, \phi_3^{0^2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\phi_0^{0^2}, \phi_3^{0^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Spinor } \psi_D^G = \begin{pmatrix} (-1) \\ \bullet \\ \bullet \\ (-1) \end{pmatrix}$$

Then complete in the EGR:

$$\frac{8\pi G}{c^4} \cdot (T_{\mu\nu} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot S_{\mu\nu}) = \frac{c}{G\hbar} \cdot \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{Minkowski} \\ \begin{array}{|c|c|c|c|} \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \end{array} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot \frac{c}{G\hbar} \cdot \begin{array}{c} \text{double Torus} \\ \begin{array}{|c|c|c|c|} \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare & \color{red}\blacksquare \\ \hline \end{array} \end{array} \right) \begin{array}{l} \text{Spin UP} \\ \text{Spin DOWN} \end{array}$$

$$= \frac{c}{G\hbar} \cdot \left[\begin{pmatrix} \phi_0^{0^2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\phi_3^{0^2} \end{pmatrix} + \frac{i}{\varphi\sqrt{2}} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda} \cdot \frac{c}{G\hbar} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -\phi_0^{0^2}, \phi_3^{0^2} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -\phi_0^{0^2}, \phi_3^{0^2} \end{pmatrix} \right]$$

$\color{red}\blacksquare$ excited
 φ ...golden ratio
pressure on a random spacedirection z

This pressure to a spacedirection should be proofable in principle!

We allow $\phi \in \mathbb{C}$

< 8 > Some important points of the Octoquintenpotential

To get the maxima, minima and the zeropoints of the potential we have to substitute $z = \phi^2$ it is enough (because of symmetry) to take a look on the positive ϕ 's. and solve the cubic equations in the bracket

$$V(\sqrt{z}) = z \cdot \left(\frac{\mu^2}{2} + \frac{\lambda^2}{4} z + \frac{\gamma^2}{8} z^3 \right) \text{ and}$$

$$V'(\sqrt{z}) = \sqrt{z} \cdot (\mu^2 + \lambda^2 \cdot z + \gamma^2 \cdot z^3)$$

We will make it short and write the results.

First the Zeropoints:

$$z_1 = u + v = -\sqrt{\frac{2C}{3}} \cdot \left(\sqrt[3]{\frac{\sqrt{27} - i\sqrt{5}}{\sqrt{32}}} + \sqrt[3]{\frac{\sqrt{27} + i\sqrt{5}}{\sqrt{32}}} \right)$$

$$z_2 = \epsilon_1 \cdot u + \epsilon_2 \cdot v$$

$$z_3 = \epsilon_2 \cdot u + \epsilon_1 \cdot v$$

$$\text{Where } \epsilon_1 = -\frac{1}{2} + i \cdot \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \text{ and } \epsilon_2 = -\frac{1}{2} - i \cdot \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$$

then

$$z_1 = -0,990839414 \times 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2C}{3}}$$

$$z_2 = 0,378466979 \times 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2C}{3}}$$

$$z_3 = 0,612372435 \times 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{2C}{3}}$$

then the zeropoints are

$$\phi_1 = -0,995409169 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8 \cdot C}{3}}$$

$$\phi_2 = 0,615196699 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8 \cdot C}{3}}$$

$$\phi_3 = 0,782542290 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8 \cdot C}{3}}$$

$$C = c^4 \cdot \varphi^2$$

c...speed of light

φ ...golden ratio

$$\phi_2 = c = 0,615196699 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8.C}{3}} = \sin(37,966214178) \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8.C}{3}}$$

$$\alpha_c = 37,966214178^\circ$$

$$\phi_3 = c \cdot \sqrt{\varphi} = 0,78254229 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8.C}{3}} = \sin(128,506061932) \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{8.C}{3}}$$

$$\alpha_{c \cdot \sqrt{\varphi}} = 128,506061932^\circ$$

Then the Maxima and the Minima :

$$z_1 = u + v = -\sqrt{\frac{C}{3}} \cdot \left(\sqrt[3]{\frac{\sqrt{37} - i \cdot \sqrt{27}}{\sqrt{64}}} + \sqrt[3]{\frac{\sqrt{37} + i \cdot \sqrt{27}}{\sqrt{64}}} \right)$$

$$z_2 = \epsilon_1 \cdot u + \epsilon_2 \cdot v$$

$$z_3 = \epsilon_2 \cdot u + \epsilon_1 \cdot v$$

Finally we have two positiv results :

$$z_{min} = 0,233475630 \times 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{C}{3}} \quad \text{and}$$

$$z_{max} = 0,725352944 \times 2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{C}{3}}$$

and one negative

$$z_3 = -(z_{max} + z_{min})$$

Then because of $z = \phi^2$

$$\phi_{min} = 0,483193160 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}} \quad \text{and}$$

$$\phi_{max} = 0,8516765489 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}}$$

In cubic equations the real zeropoints comes from the $\cos(\alpha)$ or from $\sin(90-\alpha)$ of angles (see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cubic_function).

Then for ϕ_{min} we get an angle α_{min} :

$$\phi_{min} = 0,483193160 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}} = \sin(28,894160846) \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}}$$

$\alpha_{min} = 28,894160846$ degrees is very near to the Weinbergangle

$$\sin^2(\alpha_{min}) = \sin^2(28,894160846) = 0,233475630$$

with Cardanic formular and so on we can express α_{min} by :

$$\alpha_{min} = \arcsin\left(\sqrt{-\cos\left(\frac{\arccos\left(\frac{-\sqrt{27}}{8}\right) + \pi}{3}\right)}\right) \approx 28,9^\circ$$

and for ϕ_{max} we get an angle

$$\phi_{max} = 0,8516765489 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}} = \sin(121,605508985) \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}}$$

$\alpha_{max} = 121,605508985$ degrees

$$\phi_{min} = 0,483193160 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}} \approx 0,660464.c \quad \text{c...speed of light}$$

$$\phi_{max} = 0,851676548 \times \sqrt[4]{\frac{4.C}{3}} \approx 1,164134.c$$

In cubic equations the real zeropoints comes from the $\cos(\alpha)$ or from $\sin(90-\alpha)$ of angles (see https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cubic_function).

Geometric interpretation of the roots (zeropoints) in cubic equations with 3 real zeropoints

graphical zero points of the derivation of the
(radicalized $\phi^2 = z$) Oktoquintessential potential

Hint : On our special OQP (Octoquintessential potential) the zero points (spheres) comes from a pentagon.

< 9 > Conclusions

Dark Energy comes by definition from the Octoquintessential potential (the second term in the potential).

Dark Matter could be the W , Z Bosons and the particles by the SU(5) Symmetry (adjoint and fundamental presentation).

APPENDIX I

1) The 16 – Cell

On the 16 – Cell each vertizes is connected by an edge to all other vertizes except the opposite one!

We have 4 disjunct such pairs which are not connected by an edge.

Now exchanging this points which are not connected is an automorphism (for example p_1 with p_1 -line) because p_1 has the same connections as p_1 line. So at all we generate $2^4 = 16$ automorphisms by this actions because we can say for all 4 pairs 0 means pair IS NOT exchanged and 1 for pair IS exchanged. So every binary code like $(0, 1, 0, 0)$ is an automorphism.

But this are not all automorphism. Independent from that we can permute p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4 when we simultaneously permute their opposite points.

For example :

$$\begin{aligned} p_1 &\rightarrow p_2 \\ \bar{p}_1 &\rightarrow \bar{p}_2 \end{aligned}$$

This give us $4! = 24$ automorphisms independent from the 16 automorphisms before. So at all we get $16 \cdot 24 = 384$ automorphisms.

With this we can divide the $Aut(C_{16})$ into $AutOpposite(C_{16})$ and $AutFakt(C_{16})$ so that $Aut(C_{16}) = AutOpposite(C_{16}) \times AutFakt(C_{16}) = 16 \times 4!$.

$AutOpposite(C_{16})$ are the Automorphisms of the 16–Cell C_{16} which comes from exchanging the opposite vertizes (points).

$AutFakt(C_{16})$ are the Automorphisms of the 16–Cell C_{16} which comes from permutating p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4 vertizes (points) as described above.

$AutFakt(C_{16})$ is simply the permutation – group $Sym(4) = S_4$.

Embedding (projection) the 16–Cell into the quartenionic subgroups of the Octoquintenfield : See also Quaterniongroup Q8!

APPENDIX II

Our target is to show that

$$\Lambda \cdot l_p^2 = \frac{16}{\varphi} \cdot N^2 = \frac{16}{\varphi} \cdot \left(\frac{\phi_{\min}}{c} \cdot \frac{1}{48!} \right)^2 \approx \frac{2,8}{10^{122}}$$

For that we start with the Combinatorial – Form and going back to the Einstein – Form of the OQP.

On the combinatorial form we have set $c = h = G = 1$.

$$V(\phi) = N^4 \cdot \left(-8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^2 + 16 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^4 - 8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^8 \right) \quad \boxed{N = \frac{\phi_{\min}}{c} \cdot \frac{1}{48!}}$$

We will take this back and get

$$V(\phi) = \left(\frac{P_p}{2\pi} \right)^2 \cdot N^4 \cdot \left(-8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^2 + 16 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^4 - 8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^8 \right)$$

With the relation

$$P_p \cdot l_p^2 = \frac{c^4}{G}$$

we get

$$V(\phi) = \left(\frac{c^4}{2\pi G} \cdot \frac{1}{l_p^2} \right)^2 \cdot N^4 \cdot \left(-8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^2 + 16 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^4 - 8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^8 \right) \quad \left| \cdot \frac{\Lambda^2}{\Lambda^2} \right.$$

Then

$$V(\phi) = \left(\frac{\Lambda c^4}{2\pi G} \cdot \frac{1}{\Lambda l_p^2} \right)^2 \cdot N^4 \cdot \left(-8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^2 + 16 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^4 - 8 \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c\sqrt{\varphi}} \right|^8 \right) \quad \left| \cdot \frac{\varphi^2}{\varphi^2} \cdot \frac{4^2}{4^2} \right.$$

Then

$$V(\phi) = \left(\frac{\Lambda c^4}{8\pi G} \right)^2 \cdot \left(\frac{4^2}{\Lambda l_p^2 \varphi} \right)^2 \cdot N^4 \cdot \left(-\frac{\varphi}{2} \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c} \right|^2 + \left| \frac{\phi}{c} \right|^4 - \frac{1}{2 \cdot \varphi^2} \cdot \left| \frac{\phi}{c} \right|^8 \right)$$

Comparing with the Einstein – Form this must be 1.

Then

$$\boxed{\Lambda \cdot l_p^2 = \frac{16}{\varphi} \cdot \left(\frac{v}{48!} \right)^2} \quad v = \frac{\phi_{\min}}{c}$$

QED.

With this formular we can assign an exact speed to the cosmological constant Λ .

We use the relation :

$$v^2 = \frac{1}{r^2} \cdot \frac{G \cdot \hbar}{c}$$

then for $\Lambda = \frac{1}{r^2}$ and formular above we get

$$v_\Lambda^2 = \Lambda \cdot \frac{G \cdot \hbar}{c} = \frac{16}{\varphi} \cdot \frac{1}{l_p^2} \cdot \left(\frac{v}{48!} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{G \cdot \hbar}{c} = \frac{16}{\varphi} \cdot c^2 \cdot \left(\frac{v}{48!} \right)^2 = \frac{16}{\varphi} \cdot \left(\frac{\phi_{\min}}{48!} \right)^2 \text{ then}$$

$$\boxed{v_\Lambda = \pm \frac{4 \cdot \phi_{\min}}{\sqrt{\varphi} \cdot 48!} \approx \pm \frac{1,673}{10^{61}} \cdot c}$$

Assumption 1

Calculating backward from the Combinatorial – to the Einstein form of the Oktoquintenpotential (see < 3.5 > and APPENDIX III) we get the formular :

$$\Lambda \cdot l_p^2 = \frac{16}{\varphi} \cdot \left(\frac{v}{48!} \right)^2$$

l_p ...Plancklength

$v = \frac{\phi_{\min}}{c}$ $\phi_{\min}$...minima of the potential, c ...speed of light

Λ ...cosmological constant

this leads by

$$\rho_{vac} = \rho_{\Lambda} = \Lambda \cdot \frac{c^2}{8\pi G} = \frac{16}{\varphi} \cdot \left(\frac{v}{48!}\right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{l_p^2} \cdot \frac{c^2}{8\pi G} = \frac{4}{2\pi\varphi} \cdot \left(\frac{v}{48!}\right)^2 \cdot \rho_p$$

to

$$\frac{\rho_{\Lambda}}{\rho_p} = \frac{4}{2\pi\varphi} \cdot \left(\frac{v}{48!}\right)^2$$

ρ_p ...Planckdensity

then with the formular in < 3.2 > we get the "mass of the vacuum particle"

$$m_{\Lambda} = m_p \cdot \left(\frac{\rho_{\Lambda}}{\rho_p}\right)^{\frac{1}{4}} = m_p \cdot \left(\frac{4}{2\pi\varphi} \cdot \left(\frac{v}{48!}\right)^2\right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \approx 4,032113175 \times 10^{-39} \text{ kg}$$

m_p ...Planckmass

then by the assumption (see < 3.2 >)

$$m_H = 4.16! \cdot v \cdot m_{\Lambda}$$

we get the Higgs mass as

$$m_H = 4.16! \cdot m_p \cdot \left(\frac{4}{2\pi\varphi} \cdot \left(\frac{v^3}{48!}\right)^2\right)^{\frac{1}{4}}$$

In words :

we see by this formular that we get the Higgs mass by the Planck mass natural constants π , golden ratio φ and combinatorial factors.